

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.102>

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:12F50A3B-13C0-40BC-B34C-73A73ECEDCCD>

● Acknowledgments for Volume 1 (October 2024–December 2025)

Volume 1 of *The Indochina Entomologist (ICE)* is nearing completion. Including the contents of the forthcoming issue, there are a total of 103 issues, distributed among 12 topics (number of issues in parentheses):

Acknowledgments (1)	Fauna / 区系 (5)
Biography (1)	Genetics (1)
Biology (1)	New Record(s) / 新纪录 (23)
Catalogue / 名录 (1)	New Taxon / New Taxa (51)
Contents (1)	Rediscovery (2)
Erratum (2)	Revision / 修订 (6)
Evolution (1)	Taxonomic Act(s) / Taxonomic Changes (7)

The contents of Volume 1 of *ICE* comprise the following taxonomic contributions:

Insects: 72 new species; 3 new subspecies; new national records for 10 genera and 28 species; new provincial records for 6 genera and 39 species; 2 reinstated species; 6 new combinations; 7 new species-group synonyms; 1 genus-group replacement name.

Spiders: 5 new genera; 5 new species; new national records for 15 species; new provincial records for 2 species; 1 reinstated genus; 11 new combinations; 10 new species-group synonyms.

Unionids: 2 new genera; 3 new species; 1 new combination; 1 new species-group synonym.

● Acknowledgements to the authors

First and foremost, the Editorial Board of *ICE* extends its sincerest gratitude to all authors who contributed to Volume 1. For this inaugural volume, we received valuable manuscripts from **148** scholars representing **12** countries. Each contribution has been a cornerstone in the establishment of the journal; the richness of the content and the diversity of perspectives they represent together constitute the journal's valuable inaugural legacy. This body of knowledge and the enthusiasm of entomologists from around the world are our firmest foundation. We warmly look forward to your continued interest in and support for the journal as we pursue future scholarly endeavors.

● Acknowledgements to the Typesetting Team

The Editorial Board of *ICE* extends its heartfelt gratitude to two early-career taxonomists who volunteered their time on a part-time, unpaid basis to undertake the journal's typesetting work. Over the past several months, and despite their heavy commitments to research and study, these colleagues have applied professional skill and unfailing enthusiasm to the demanding tasks of manuscript layout, typesetting, and copyediting. Their meticulous attention to formatting details and careful refinement of the journal's visual presentation provided an indispensable foundation that enabled us to present Volume 1 to readers on schedule and in a clear, polished form. These selfless contributions beyond the call of duty exemplify the deep commitment and sense of responsibility that young scholars bring to building our disciplinary community. We not only gratefully acknowledge their hard work as typesetting editors but also deeply respect the collegial spirit they have shown as practicing taxonomists. The smooth operation

of the journal depends on such solid and generous support. We sincerely wish them every success and a bright future in their research careers.

Kai-Xi CUI (11)

Hua-Zhao LI (29)

Cheng-Bin WANG

● Acknowledgements to the reviewers

The Editorial Board of *ICE* thanks the following **76** individuals for voluntarily committing valuable professional time and expertise to the peer review of manuscripts considered for inclusion in Volume 1 of the journal. Special thanks are due to those who reviewed multiple manuscripts (number of times in parentheses). The quality and scientific stature of the journal depend on the conscientious efforts of these reviewers.

Xing-Long BAI (2)

Zhuo-Heng JIANG (1)

Ji-Shen WANG (3)

Jan BOSSELAERS (1)

Axel KALLIES (1)

Ping WANG (8)

En-Yong CHEN (1)

Denis KEITH (1)

Chao WU (1)

Hui CHEN (1)

Jiří KOLIBÁČ (1)

Chun-Lan XIAN (1)

Jia-Heng CHEN (2)

Song-Yun LANG (1)

Hong-Quan XIANG (3)

Jian-Yu CHEN (1)

Hua-Zhao LI (5)

Guang-Lin XIE (4)

Ye CHEN (1)

Wen-Jian LI (1)

Jiao XIE (1)

Zhe-Yu CHEN (1)

Yi-Hang LI (1)

Hao XU (16)

Zhi-Lin CHEN (1)

Zhu LI (1)

Shu-Lin YANG (1)

Zhi-Teng CHEN (2)

Cheng-Qing LIAO (2)

Yu-Xia YANG (1)

Sarah CREWS (1)

Mei-Ying LIN (1)

Xiong-Yan YIN (2)

Bastian DROLSHAGEN (1)

Ye-Jie LIN (7)

Zi-Xu YIN (2)

Chuan-Bu GAO (1)

Jun-Jie LIU (1)

Hiroyuki YOSHITOMI (1)

Han GAO (1)

Qin-Peng LIU (1)

Kun YU (3)

Hao-Ran GAO (4)

Zhen-Hua LIU (3)

Cai-Xia YUAN (1)

Lei GAO (1)

Yun-Long MA (5)

Alireza ZAMANI (1)

Charles R. HADDAD (1)

Tatsuya NIISATO (1)

Zhi-Hong ZHAN (1)

David L. HANCOCK (1)

Zhao PAN (1)

Jia-Zhi ZHANG (1)

Tian-Long HE (3)

Lu QIU (5)

Ming-Zhi ZHAO (4)

Yue-Ming HE (1)

Yong-Ying RUAN (1)

Yu-Cheng ZHENG (1)

Shao-Ji HU (1)

Guido SABATINELLI (1)

De-Yao ZHOU (1)

Hao HUANG (1)

Zi-Hao SHEN (1)

Gu-Chun ZHOU (1)

Jia-Long HUANG (2)

Danniella SHERWOOD (1)

Jiang ZHU (10)

Si-Yao HUANG (7)

Hong-Liang SHI (1)

Carsten ZORN (2)

Chun-Yan JIANG (1)

Kaoru WADA (1)

Ri-Xin JIANG (1)

Fa-Lei WANG (2)

● Acknowledgements to the Editorial Board

Finally, the Editorial Board of *ICE* extends its highest respect and sincerest gratitude to all members. Over the past year, your deep scholarly expertise, rigorous approach to peer review, and selfless dedication have provided each manuscript in Volume 1 with professional insight and invaluable guidance. You have been not only a firm foundation for the quality of our manuscripts but also a guiding light for the journal's academic direction and ethical standards. This uncompensated service lies at the heart of the journal's ability to establish itself and earn the trust of the scholarly community. We are profoundly grateful to count such distinguished scholars among our colleagues, and we look forward to continuing to work with you in the year ahead to advance and enrich research in our field. Thank you sincerely.

Associate Editors:

Tian-Long HE (Coleoptera: Lucanidae)

Jiang ZHU (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)

Subject Editors:

Zhi-Teng CHEN (Dermaptera, Embioptera and Plecoptera) (exited)

Hao-Ran GAO (Phasmatodea)

Harvey XUN (Hemiptera: Coreidae) (exited)

Yi-hang LI (Coleoptera: Carabidae)

Ye-Jie LIN (Araneae)

Lu QIU (Elateridae, Eucnemidae, Scarabaeinae, Blattodea)

Ji-Shen WANG (Mecoptera)

Hao XU (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae; Bibliography and Toponym of Zoology)

Zi-Xu YIN (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidea)

Advisory Board:

Zhi-Teng CHEN, Hua-Zhao LI, Xiao-Feng LI, Tian-Lang LYU, Ping WANG, Hiroyuki YOSHITOMI

